

Building Integrated Photovoltaics (Manuscript number: NRCT-24-003V1)

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Abstract |

The field of Building-integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) addresses the dual purposes of generating electricity while fulfilling functional and/or architectural functions within the building. In this review, we address the multiple facets of this interdisciplinary domain and illustrate it with several case studies, from iconic to more standard and replicable examples, with applications for roofs, façades, balcony, or for semi-transparent structures. We show how the emergence of colored solutions allows for striking or unnoticeable aesthetic effects, opening an infinite design playing field. The mainstream market, dominated by crystalline silicon with increasing efficiency and decreasing cell price, significantly influences BIPV adoption, making it economically more attractive. Quickly changing solar cells format and interconnections also create challenges for the manufacturing of BIPV elements, where small companies with local manufacturing often serve the market. Some intrinsic challenges are discussed, including regulatory aspects, fire, or potential issues with shading and hot spot, which can lead to reliability issues. The share of BIPV depends on the countries, with close to 10% in Switzerland. BIPV has a huge potential for providing and self-consuming electricity locally, and the growing maturity and possibilities offered by the technology jointly with the awareness of users, stakeholders and architects in any building project makes for prospects of tens of GW global annual installation. Technological improvements lead to increasingly attractive BIPV systems CO2 footprint and a sustainable contribution not only for decarbonization of the electricity sector but also for substituting fossil fuels used in transport and heating.

Key points |

Building-integrated photovoltaic (BIPV) converts ordinary building exteriors into silent, stationary, clean, local and potentially invisible sources of energy. The carbon footprint of energy production from a south-facing roof is 90% lower than the average energy mix of the EU27, and the net present value, is consistently favorable - except for north-facing façades - varying from €200 to €1800 per m² for rooftop installations in Europe.

1. Introduction

Today, more than 80% of the global energy demand comes from fossil fuels causing a CO₂ (a greenhouse gas) concentration of up to 419 ppm in the atmosphere¹. This results in global warming, and a related increase of sea levels and more extreme and frequent weather events that affect society, food security and health. Hence, mankind needs to rapidly transition towards renewable sources. The Sun, an abundant sustainable energy source that every year radiates to Earth 6450 times the human energy demand. Logically, photovoltaic (PV) modules that directly convert solar irradiance into electricity play a pivotal role in the energy transition^{2,3}. However, the surface required to cover the global energy demand with PV systems is huge and represents an area of about 1 million km² which causes conflicts with land use available for nature, agriculture, or forestry. Typically, PV yields one of the lowest CO₂ emissions of all energy technologies whereas their modular, flat, silent and power generating features are well suited for the co-location of generation and consumption of electricity in places where a significant share of mankind's energy is used: in buildings and urbanized areas⁴⁻⁶.

Figure 1. **Schemes and examples of integration for Building Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV).** **a** | Each surface of the buildings can be converted to multifunctional active layers which will produce the energy needed by the construction to reach net-zero or even positive energy buildings by replacing roofs, façades, balconies, blinds or canopies. **b** | BIPV is combining minimum two ways of integration from the following three: Energy, Technology and Aesthetic. [The BIPV is a construction element that serves multiple functions but at least generating electricity and one building component function].

Building-Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV) refers to photovoltaic (PV) modules that serve dual functions: generating electricity and acting as integral building components. These modules are incorporated into various parts of the building envelope, such as roofs, canopies, walls, balconies, blinds, and windows (see Figure 1). BIPV differs from Building-Applied Photovoltaics (BAPV), where conventional PV panels are simply added to the building's surface, like on roofs above traditional tiles (see Figure 1b). BAPV installations are generally cheaper and subject to different regulations since they do not contribute to the building's structural functionality or integrity.

According to the IEA PVPS Task 15, European (EN50583), and International (IEC 63092) standards, BIPV modules are considered construction products that provide essential functions as defined by the European Construction Product Regulation (CPR 305/2011). This means that BIPV modules are crucial for the building's integrity and must be replaced with equivalent construction products if removed. Architecturally, BIPV must also integrate with the building's design and aesthetics, forming a seamless part of the construction. Various building projects have shown stunning BIPV examples

in both an architectural context (Figure 2,a) and in common, traditional buildings (Figure 2.b) combining all three main way of integration: Energy, Technology and Aesthetic.

Figure 2. **Examples of Building Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV).** **a** | Iconic solar powered stadium, 2009, Taiwan. This BIPV project has been designed by Japanese architect Toyo Ito for the 2009 World Games in Taiwan, featuring 8844 regular rectangular glass-glass crystalline-silicon PV modules on its roof. The stadium's organic, open-circle design resembles a dragon wagging its tail. The PV modules contribute to a metallic snakeskin appearance, achieved through careful design with geometric irregularities. **b** | Chalet La Pedevilla, 2011-2015, Italy. Located in South Tyrol's dolomite mountains, this chalet designed by Pedevilla architects modernizes the traditional 'Paarhof' farm building. A BIPV system with 25 black mono-crystalline silicon PV modules is seamlessly integrated into the dark pine-wooden roof, achieving nearly Zero-Energy Building (nZEB) standards with 80% of the produced solar energy self-consumed. The BIPV system has a high replication potential. **c** | The facade of the Copenhagen International School is composed of over 12,000 custom-designed photovoltaic panels produced by Danish manufacturer SolarLab based on Kromatix colour. In 2017, the project and C.F Moller Architects received the Germany's Iconic Award, noting the school's innovative facade cladding. **d** | Umwelt Arena Schweiz foundation project in collaboration with René Schmid Architekten AG was awarded with the Swiss Watt D'Or in 2021. Equipped by 80 kWp of BIPV brown-red colored structured satin glass with vertical lines from Sunage Solar Buildings Skins. [The

BIPV construction can be iconic (a, c) or replicable (b, d), based on standard PV modules (a, b) or highly specific BIPV products (c, d); which brings freedom with an infinite possibility of combinations].

The performance and reliability of mainstream PV modules are excellent and due to their large volume, their price is very low, with only a few tens of € per square meter. Therefore, currently new product design and styling of PV modules are becoming important for BIPV applications, including various coloring options, shaping or curvature. At the same time, existing EU regulations support the realization of zero-emission buildings while new rules will ensure the further deployment of suitable solar energy installations in new constructions, public buildings and existing non-residential ones under renovation⁷. This broad context articulates the importance of BIPV now and in the near-future. Various reviews about BIPV can be found in literature and reports by IEA PVPS Task 15 on BIPV⁸⁻²². These reviews cover different BIPV products and BIPV applications, possible categorizations of BIPV solutions within the building envelope, colored BIPV, design approaches and methods for the realization of BIPV projects.

This review will discuss how the evolution of PV technologies has enabled BIPV (Section 2) to be illustrated by Section 3 on various BIPV projects. Section 4 will focus on the economic viability and environmental impact of BIPV, and Section 5 will discuss present and future BIPV markets. This paper won't address conventional PV modules or large scale grid-connected PV systems, but instead will refer and compare BIPV to mainstream PV modules.

2. How the evolution of PV technology enables BIPV

PV technology evolution during the last decade has increased efficiency by more than 25% and reduced costs by 90%²³. Developments in PV materials and processes and new electrical designs allow BIPV modules to enhance their performance, reliability, and aesthetical possibilities while considering construction-related requirements as building elements.

a. Solar cells: technology evolution

The efficiency of crystalline-silicon (c-Si) based PV cells and modules has increased by 0.5 to 0.6% abs/year²⁴. Top-range monocrystalline silicon (m-Si) PV modules use high-efficiency PV cells based on half-cut thin n-type wafers, back contacts, and advanced rear-side passivation techniques. This results in commercial PV modules with more than 23 % efficiency²⁵.

Multi-crystalline silicon (mc-Si) phased out, while m-Si Passivated Rear and Emitter Contact (PERC) cell is reducing its share in the global PV market. Bifacial Tunnel Oxide Passivated Contact (TOPCon) is the new mainstream m-Si technology with improved passivated contact and efficiency²⁶.

Thin film cadmium telluride (CdTe) and indium-gallium-copper selenide (CIGS) technologies are approaching c-Si efficiencies, and hydrogenated amorphous silicon (H:a-Si) is mostly used in heterojunction (SHJ) cells²⁷, which is competing in performance with TOPCon technology with PV modules efficiencies above 22%.

b. Interconnection schemes

The interconnection design of PV cells has significantly improved. Cell interconnection in the past was made by soldering two to five flat copper ribbons coated with tin-lead alloys. Nowadays, the flat ribbons are replaced by twelve or more copper wires of about 0.3 mm in diameter coated with solder, which reduces shadowing and ohmic losses²⁸. To further improve efficiency and reduce materials usage half-cut PV cells are used. All these evolutions toward improved efficiency and cost reduction make the solar cell metallization and interconnection more discrete and, overall, the PV module more aesthetic²⁹. With PV in buildings increasing, full-black modules using dark backsheets become a

standard for mainstream PV products. Figure 3 shows some examples of the mainstream photovoltaic module design.

Figure 3. **Evolution of mainstream photovoltaic module designs.** **a** | From 3 busbars to multi-wire cell interconnection, from full wafer to half-cut cells, and from small wafer 156 mm x 156 mm to large wafer: 210 mm x 210 mm. **b-d** | Evolution of screen and stencil printed finger width from 2008 to 2020 on silicon solar cells, Comparison of SEM cross-sectional images of typical screen-printed fingers using fire-through Ag paste from 2013 to 2020. [Evolution of mainstream PV passing from flat ribbons to multi-wire enables better aesthetics]. [Figure adapted from © 2024 U. Desai, Photovoltaics solar cells and modules technology developments for solar architecture, espazium AG, ISSN: 2813-1789²⁸](#) © 2023 A. Lorenz, S. Tepner., [Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications published by John Wiley & Sons Ltd²⁹](#).

c. *The BIPV design parameters*

There is a variety of design options for the different materials of a PV module³⁰. From the lowest to the highest degree of customization, the PV cell pattern and colour, the module electrical design, and the colouring of the back and front sheets. All PV module technologies are suitable for colour change and transparency modulation. Thin film technologies can offer a variety of surface visual appearances, limited by cost constraints linked to the production volume³¹

The surface can be glossy or matte, depending on the texture of the front materials, although specular reflection could disturb pedestrians or drivers^{32 33}.

d. *Colouring technologies*

Coloring of the PV modules is one of the first steps for a full integration into building environment³⁴. The coloring can highlight the technology, when the solar cells are colorized by varying the anti-reflective coating thickness³⁵ or it can hide the PV cells to transform the solar module aspect into a conventional construction element³⁶. Multiple hiding solutions exist in particular colouring film embedded in the front encapsulant³⁷, coloured glass with a coating³⁸ or directly in the bulk³⁹. Coloured glass in the bulk has the highest reliability but the flexibility is reduced and the cost high, the colored film has the highest flexibility in term of production of uniform color as the foil can be cut at the PV module dimension without the need to order in advance the glass at the right color and dimension like for the colored and coated glass. Image printing on the glass is an advantage of digital ceramic printing (DCP)³⁸ but with the risk to induce hot spot in case of solar cells current mismatch.

The coloring technology can be based on pigments, interferential coatings¹² or fluorescent dyes⁴⁰. Power of the colored PV module compared to a black one can be reduced up to 45% with clear tone like white or light grey, to only 6% with interferential blue color and even some power gain can be expected based on fluorescent dyes converting UV to blue light⁴⁰.

Semi-transparent BIPV module can be coloured, simply by spacing the opaque solar cells or directly from the cell technology with thin reddish amorphous-silicium (a-Si)⁴¹ or perovskite solar cells (PSC)⁴², blueish or greenish organic solar cells (OPV)⁴³ as explained in previous subsection. Reliability of colored PV is of great importance and should pass similar test as the building's element, in particular extended UV-irradiation and damp-heat test should be evaluated as discussed in the following subsection.

Figure 4. **Example of coloured BIPV modules.** **a** | BIPV building of the Copenhagen International School with blue green Kromatix glass. Images courtesy of Kromatix™ SA. **b** | Façade of Computer Science Building of the University of Belfast with Vanceva coloured foils. Images courtesy of Vanceva. **c** | Examples of realizations using colored films integrated in PV modules by Compaz. Images courtesy of Association Compaz. **d** | SUM prototype façade from Kameleon Solar. Images provided by Kameleon Solar | Team SUM. **e** | Freesuns project in Ferlens, Switzerland, with different tones of terracotta solar tiles. Images courtesy of Freesuns. **f** | Building in Zürich, Switzerland, with terracotta foil from Solaxess. Images provided 3S Swiss Solar Solutions AG. [The BIPV modules can disappear in the building environment or become a masterpiece]. [Figure adapted from ref 34](#).

e. Performance & Reliability

Due to reduced rear-side ventilation, BIPV modules are prone to higher operating temperatures than ground-mounted PV modules (temperature differences can approach $\sim 20^{\circ}\text{C}$ ^{44–46}). Exposure to higher operating temperatures may impact the long-term reliability and durability of BIPV modules by accelerating some degradation modes⁴⁷. Materials, particularly polymers, may age faster incurring a loss of critical properties⁴⁸, while thermomechanical stresses (e.g. at solder joints or other interfaces) may increase⁴⁹.

BIPVs also suffer partial shading more often due to the presence of nearby objects, such as chimneys, trees, or neighbouring buildings. To avoid hotspots events (e.g. very high temperatures as high as $130\text{-}150^{\circ}\text{C}$ that can build up in the shaded areas) the functionality of the bypass diodes should be checked⁵⁰. In the long run, the occurrence of hotspots may prospectively lead to the generation of other failure modes, such as encapsulant discolouration, interconnection failures and cell cracks, delamination, and loss of electrical insulation. If the temperature and frequency of these hotspots are high, the module's reliability and safety may be at risk.

BIPV modules may therefore require dedicated efforts in the design and material selection to make them more robust against these peculiar operating conditions^{51,52}. On a system scale, it is recommended that BIPV system designs look for solutions that limit as much as possible the occurrence of partial shading during the central hours of the day when solar irradiance becomes higher.

3. Designing BIPV buildings

Considering the wide variety of BIPV components available today, it is hard to imagine that architects willing to incorporate this technology into their buildings would struggle to find solutions that are technically sound, energy-efficient, and aesthetically pleasing. However, in the past, this was not granted. In the following a timeline of the evolution of the use of PV in buildings, with specific reference to the search of a proper architectural language, will be given. In doing this, some important advancements, made possible by the new available technologies (size, dimension, color, interconnections), the cost and conversion efficiencies, will be given.

a. Market segment & customization. (see below)

Should a date be given to the first show of PV in the landscape of architects, this should be in the late 90s, when research on the development of BIPV was funded. Two were the main approaches to address the building market: the search for new PV visually appealing components, or for technologically compatible components, fitting to the existing building technological sub-systems. In both cases the focus is on the PV modules.³⁶

In the same years, while researchers were playing with the PV technology in order to morph a technical element into a building element; and architects for finding an appropriate architectural use of PV that could be coherent with the design of the buildings, and, also, with the new born “green” narrative associated to the buildings.

Along the narrative of BIPV, a sparkling dialogue between PV and communities or architects and engineers, that started over 30 years ago, it is possible to extract different themes. One is: the different use of PV in prestigious & iconic projects vs. multiplication and mass-produced PV elements. Another important theme is the relationship between PV and the building energy balance, the clear dividing line between buildings where PV can be used as a “jewel”, on very small areas, and others where PV has to be used in large areas to fulfill the whole building energy demand³⁸.

In the following some examples will be given, waving from a use of PV that emphasizes its presence in the building envelope in search of new, symbolic, energy oriented new meanings, and a different use that tries to make it completely hidden into the building envelope.

b. Case Studies.

Building integrated PV start in the 70's with the solar pioneers as shown by the Solar One experimental house from University of Delaware, the hybrid system of solar thermal and solar PV based on CdS/Cu_xS technology was integrated in the roof (Fig. 5.0)^{53,54}. In the 80's a genuine building was raised for hosting two institutes: the first one focusing on solar energy and the other on producing hydrogen at low cost: the HySolar building was designed and constructed in a very short period of time, the idea of free equilibrium provided an uninhibited source of freshness for the architecture (Fig. 5.1).

The iconic value of a building, and its uniqueness, does not necessarily lie in the use of special PV components, but can be rather achieved by using standard PV modules in a non-standard mode. In the case of the solar townhouses built in the new district Freiburg-Rieselfeld (DE) in 1998 (Fig. 5a), the building is unique thanks to its shape, no matter what PV is used. On the contrary, in the Nieuwland housing project (Fig. 5b), built in Amersfoort (NL) in 2000³⁷, the use of PV is

inconspicuously melded into the building by incorporating the PV modules into the envelope in a very “discreet” way that makes this approach replicable.

The high-profile Mont-Cenis Academy, built in Herne (DE) in 1999³⁷, is a parallelepiped, composed of few architectural elements (structure, skin) and materials (wood, glass, PV glass, aluminum) made possible by the use of customized, rectangular, glass-glass, PV modules.

As dynamic façades were emerging to render the indoor environment comfortable for the inhabitants, PV was also included in the idea of “dynamism” by the architects. Ideally, PV is a dynamic material, as it responds to the sun condition and the presence of people, this concept is materialized on the NEST building close to Zürich where small lightweight PV modules are mounted on actuators fixed on rod-net structure to be used as an outer layer of a glazed façade⁵⁵ (Fig. 5d). Another example of dynamic building is the Shigeru Ban's La Seine Musicale, a music complex near Paris finished in 2027, featuring an egg-shaped auditorium and a wall of solar panels that move to follow the path of the sun (Fig. 5i).

A different expression of dynamism is the Green Pix media façade, built on the occasion of the 2008 Olympic Games in Beijing (China) (Fig. 5e). Green Pix is a media façade composed of functional layers in which PV cells are integrated into the external glass layer, and LEDs behind it. Thus, the dynamic element is the LED, with a general effect of a dynamic façade.

Another important influential factor for the use of PV in architecture is the requirement for a Net Zero Energy Balance, because it sets a very strict relationship between the energy consumption of the building and the size of the energy generation system. It is simple to grasp that PV becomes bigger and therefore more visible. So, new thinking is necessary on how to accommodate all the necessary PV into the building envelope. From the design point of view this can lead to several options, and here we will give two examples. In the case of the SIEEB building (Fig. 5f), built in Beijing in 2016, the façade transforms into “wings”. The PV modules are located on sheds, and the building becomes “rarefied”, in search of an extension of its surface, to accommodate all the necessary PV.

On the contrary, in the case of Green Dot Building (Fig. 5g), built in Inglewood (US) in 2013, the building is very “compact”, with the whole façade completely covered with standard PV modules.

As a (temporary) end point of the narrative of the architectural use of PV we suggest the point when PV becomes invisible. The example in Fig. 5h, built in Zurich (CH) in 2016, is a very evident of how this use of PV challenges the perception, as PV modules are morphed into colored, opaque glasses. In detail: the façade is composed of a few types (size) rectangular modules showing an opaque, uniform, grey surface. Another recent feature of BIPV is the possibility of having picture or drawings on the façade giving an infinite possibility of expression as shown on the renovated façade of Solartech production site in Genk (Fig. 5j). Counterintuitive white colored BIPV can be used today, giving a lightness in the buildings as shown by the Quzhou Riverside Scenic Belt management house, in China built in 2019 with a total capacity of 24 kWp (Fig. 5k). Finally, renovation using PV will become more important in the future and should be possible also for protected buildings. FreeSuns has demonstrated a perfect integration of solar tiles in the historical buildings dated from 1914, Le Collège des Parc in Neuchatel, Switzerland, with more than 20 thousands of single tiles (Fig. 5l).

The external surface of the module looks different than the standard one, as additional layers have been added on the external side of the module, or special treatments have been made on the glass surface, for achieving desired visual effects, namely BIPV to be invisible (see section 3a).

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Figure 5. **BIPV Case Studies.** **0** | “Solar One” house, University of Delaware, Newark, USA, 1973^{53,54}
1 | Hysolar building, Stuttgart, Germany, 1987. Design: Günter Behnisch & Partner. **a** | Solar townhouses, Freiburg, Germany, 1998. Design: Thomas Spiegelhalter . **b** | Nieuwland housing project, Amersfoort, The Netherlands, 2000. Design: a team of Dutch architects. **c** | Akademie Mont-Cenis, 1999. Design: Jourda e Perraudin, Herne, Germany. **d** | NEST HiLo Dynamic photovoltaic building envelopes, Dübendorf, Switzerland, 2017-21. Design: A/S Team. **e** | Green Pix, Beijing, China, 2008. Design: Simone Giostra Picture courtesy of Simone Giostra. **f** | SIEEB building, Beijing, China, 2006. Design: MCA Mario Cucinella Architects. **g** | Green Dot, Inglewood, US, 2013. Design: Brooks + Scarpa Architects Picture courtesy of Larry Scarpa @Jon Linden. **h** | Apartment building on Hofwiesen- and Rothstrasse, Renovation and expansion, Zürich (CH), 2016. Design: Viridén + partner. Picture courtesy of Karl Viridén. **i** | La Seine Musicale, Paris, France, 2017. Design: Shigeru Ban Picture courtesy of Didier Boy de la Tour. **j** | The solar façade of Soltech's factory in Genk, Belgium, 2023. Photo: Bjørn Vijlbrief. **k** | Quzhou Riverside Scenic Belt management house, the project construction in November 2019, Qujiang District, Quzhou, China, 2019. the installed capacity of the project is 24 kWp for self-use. . **l** | Le Collège des Parcs, Neuchatel, Switzerland, 1914, renovation 2024, Roof Renovation and pictures: FreeSuns. [The evolution of the BIPV is directly linked to the evolution of the PV module to be better integrated but also to the imagination of architect to use standard glass/glass PV module as a construction materials].

Another suggestion for presenting Figure 5: Standard PV module Data origine
 OurWorldInData.org/energy

c. Standardization and Legislation

Standardization and legislation for Building Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV) are inherently complex due to the necessity of addressing both the electrotechnical and construction domains.

Standards in the construction domain prioritize the structural integrity, durability, and aesthetic integration of BIPV systems. For example, ISO 2394 and the Eurocodes developed by CEN (European Committee of Standardization), as well as regulations provided by the American Society of Civil Engineers such as ASCE 7, focus on ensuring that BIPV panels contribute to the overall stability of the building and blend well with architectural designs⁵⁹.

In contrast, standards in the electrotechnical domain focus primarily on electrical safety, performance efficiency, and the reliability of PV systems. These standards include measures for preventing electrical hazards, ensuring proper insulation, and maintaining optimal energy output. Key standards

in this domain include those developed by the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) and the International Organization for Standardization (ISO).

One significant standard in the BIPV field is the EN 50583 series, "Photovoltaic in Buildings," issued in 2016 at the European level. These standards address both the construction and electrotechnical aspects of BIPV systems, aiming to provide comprehensive guidelines for their integration into buildings. Additionally, new work item proposals have been launched internationally to further refine BIPV standards. Notable among these are ISO/TS 18178 (Laminated Solar PV Glass) developed by ISO TC160 (Glass in Building), and several standards within the IEC technical committee TC82 (Photovoltaics). In 2017, a new working group within IEC TC82 (82/1339/DC) was established to develop IEC 63092, "Building Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV)," which was released in 2020.

A detailed analysis of the requirements and specifications for BIPV can be found in the report of IEA PVPS Task 15 (IEA PVPS T15), which provides a comprehensive overview of the standards and best practices in this evolving field⁶⁰.

Fire safety is a critical consideration in the design and implementation of BIPV systems due to the integration of electrical components into building structures. The fire performance of BIPV systems must be thoroughly evaluated to ensure they do not pose additional risks compared to traditional building materials. Key concerns include the potential for electrical faults, such as short circuits or arc faults, which can ignite fires, as well as the behavior of photovoltaic materials under fire conditions. To address these concerns, several standards and guidelines have been developed as for example the IEC 61730: Photovoltaic (PV) Module Safety Qualification that provides requirements for the safety testing of PV modules, including fire resistance. It ensures that PV modules meet stringent safety standards to minimize fire risks (similarly in America UL 1703: Standard for Flat-Plate Photovoltaic Modules and Panels). To provide a classification system for the fire performance of building components exposed to external fire CEN has developed the EN 1350-1:2018 reaction to fire of construction products. This standard is relevant for evaluating the fire resistance of building and BIPV systems when used as building element (roof or façade). The standard for the classification of construction products containing combustible materials, such as photovoltaic modules, should refer to SN EN ISO 11925-2 and SN EN 13823, called SBI (Single Burning Item). Additionally, to product classification, building codes and fire safety regulations, such as the International Building Code (IBC) and National Fire Protection Association (NFPA) standards, include provisions for the installation of photovoltaic systems and building elements. These regulations address aspects such as fire barriers to ensure that BIPV systems do not compromise the integrity of fire barriers and compartmentalization within buildings and access for firefighters or consideration related to emergency shutdown.

Ongoing research and collaboration among standardization bodies, industry stakeholders, and regulatory authorities are crucial to advancing fire safety in BIPV applications.

4. Economic viability & Environmental Impact

The economic and ecological competitiveness of Building Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV) largely hinges on key drivers such as initial capital costs (technology costs, installation expenses), location (irradiation levels, electricity grid, incentive schemes), and building characteristics (consumption profile, sector coupling, etc.)^{61,62}.

a. Building PV usage and economics

In contrast to roof mounted PV, BIPV requires additional efforts for its integration into the building envelope. The BIPV layer, however, can replace otherwise necessary building materials for façade and roof cladding, which allows to partly offset the costs for a BIPV installation. From a building perspective, the economic performance of BIPV is determined by the balance between costs and benefits. Costs include the construction and installation of the building envelope including the PV

layer (Fig. 6a) and its maintenance. For building operation, the running costs of energy consumption of the building and the benefits through self-consumption and feed-in tariffs are combined¹⁸. As feed-in tariffs are often lower than the grid electricity price, self-consumption of self-generated electricity is therefore often economically beneficial (Fig. 6b). Some building applications such as space cooling naturally exhibit a good overlap between solar energy generation and on-site usage. Measures to otherwise increase self-consumption include energy management systems, dynamic operation of appliances, and load shifting through thermal storage, such as for space heating and domestic hot water. Additionally, self-consumption can be enhanced through sector coupling: electric vehicles can be charged during solar peaks to reduce grid demand and dependency, thus linking mobility to the building sector⁶³. Bi-directional charging and discharging via vehicle-to-grid (V2G) allows for the spatial and temporal shift of solar energy to consumers without own generation capacities^{64,65}. On a larger scale, connecting multiple buildings for joint generation and utilization of solar energy allows for better matching of demand and supply, reducing storage needs. Forming 'energy communities' of prosumers, entities that both produce and consume energy, allows for joint generation, utilization and sharing of solar energy, reducing individual expenditures for energy and offering income opportunities through excess production⁶⁶. Implementation examples include local electricity markets for exchange and trading between prosumers and the grid⁶⁷.

b. Economic competitiveness of BIPV

Beyond the building, the economic viability of BIPV is heavily influenced by its political and economic boundary conditions. This is highlighted in a recent study by Schmidt, *et al.* for Switzerland, in which they identify a vast variety of local policies such as taxation rules, building codes, subsidy schemes and large differences in feed-in tariffs, which render PV installations from highly profitable to economically unfavorable⁶⁸.

As Weerasinghe *et al.* describe, the most widespread economic parameter used to assess the economic performance of BIPV are Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) and Net Present Value (NPV)⁶⁹. LCOE denotes the relation between lifecycle costs and lifecycle energy generation, expressed as cost per unit of energy generated (kWh). NPV is the difference between the present value of cash inflows and the present value of cash outflows over a period. Recent studies estimate the average LCOE of current BIPV systems (all façade orientations and rooftop) in European Union Member states including Norway and Switzerland at 0.15 €/kWh including the costs for building envelope material but excluding benefits from feed-in tariffs, while the average electricity price is 0.18 €/kWh, thus making BIPV cost-competitive on average (Fig. 6c)⁶¹. Due to the low electricity prices in some countries, economic incentives such as feed-in tariffs are nevertheless necessary.

The specific cost-competitiveness of BIPV is thus subject to local conditions. Italian case studies analyzed present positive NPV due to favorable irradiation conditions and high electricity costs, with NPV up to 877€ for each squared meter of BIPV system installed considering the entire life of the system⁷⁰⁻⁷³. Conversely, in countries like the Netherlands, competitiveness is rarely achieved due to the combination of unfavorable factors, low compensable retail prices and poor irradiation conditions. BIPV already is an attractive investment in many locations and cases, for example when roof systems are applied to residential housing⁷⁴. However, the situation is less straightforward for façade systems, which can be economically uncompetitive except where support schemes for PV and/or irradiation are particularly generous (e.g. in Switzerland). Since the COVID-2 pandemic and the war in Ukraine, many parameters, however, (e.g. inflation and discount rates, cost of capital and hardware, retail electricity prices, etc.) have changed, which may limit the validity of these numbers today⁷⁵.

The economic viability and competitiveness of BIPV are improving driven by technological advancements, policy support, and innovative cost-reduction strategies. In particular, the concept of mass customization is emerging as a key strategy to enhance the cost-effectiveness of BIPV,

producing building-integrated modules in larger quantities while allowing for customization to fit specific architectural needs⁷⁶.

c. Maintenance and end-of-life replacement

In general, a state-of-art BIPV system design should allow the possibility to access, service and replace malfunctioning PV panels or other balance of system (BOS) components. This is critical in safeguarding the profitability and the pay-back time of the BIPV investment. However, for some BIPV installations accessibility might prove difficult, as well as the availability of spare parts with the proper size and design, particularly when the modules are custom-made. For these reasons, operation and maintenance (O&M) costs may turn expensive for BIPV and may be difficult to quantify beforehand. It is therefore advisable to install state-of-art monitoring systems, that may help in the early detection of failures and plan timely interventions and retrofits^{78,79}.

Similarly, easy accessibility of the BIPV system at the end-of-life (EOL) is critical and should be properly addressed during the design phase. The BIPV system is in fact a full constituent of the building envelope and its EOL removal cannot happen without a timely substitution with new BIPV or with conventional building elements.

With respect to circularity, reuse, and recyclability, BIPV panels will not differ significantly from conventional PV panels, for which the glass, junction boxes and aluminum frames can be recycled easily, whereas attempts are made to improve the recycling of Si and other precious elements, such as silver^{80,81}. As of today, the industry experience with BIPV plants approaching their EOL is however still limited.

Figure 6. **Cost, carbon footprint and net present value (NPV) of BIPV In Europe. a** | Comparison of the end-user cost of various ventilated façade (rainscreen façade) solutions, as of 2019⁷⁷. **b** | Probability distributions of the carbon intensity of PV systems for all orientations and all European

countries⁶². The distribution is largely affected by the different annual insolation levels of the different capital cities. The same values are compared to the distribution of the CI of national electricity mixes (Right). S-opta: south-facing at optimal tilt; S-90°: south-facing at 90° (W-90° and N-90° refer to north- and west-facing façades, respectively). **c** | The cumulative NPV (€/sq.m.) of BIPV systems for building skins with different orientations in European countries⁶¹. [The cost of BIPV is in the same range as standard construction element, the carbon intensity and the NPV are always positive for BIPV apart for north-facing façade]. [Figure adapted from](#) ^{61,62,77}.

d. Life-cycle Assessment (LCA)

Recent Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of PV reflect the huge improvements of the technology to reduce its carbon intensity (CI) in the last decades^{82,83}. A recent study encompassing the whole Europe has examined how integrating photovoltaic systems (IPV) into buildings and infrastructure, particularly on sub-optimal surface orientations - a common scenario for PV in constructed environments - can influence the carbon intensity (CI) metrics for solar electricity generated by BIPV⁶².

The mean values obtained for the CI of solar electricity generated in BIPV (whose distribution is influenced primarily by the different latitudes) corresponds to 36 gCO₂-eq/kWh for an optimally oriented rooftop PV installation, which is only a tenth of the mean values for the national electricity mixes of European countries: 375 gCO₂-eq/kWh. For façades, this corresponds to 52, 71, and 214 gCO₂-eq/kWh, respectively, for S-, W-/E-, and N-facing façades (see Fig. 6b). Notably, thanks to technological progress and the possibility to use “greener” electricity mixes in manufacturing, the potential to halve these figures by 2030 already exists. For most countries, the integration of PV in façades (often including N-facing PV façades) would support a transition towards a carbon-neutral electricity mix. Additionally, the strategy of electrification of transportation and heating sectors with renewable energy sources is fundamental to reducing carbon emissions across the entire energy system, which will necessitate the expansion of clean power generation capacity like BIPV.

5. Current & Future Markets

BIPV market is very diversified and difficult to monitor due to its complexity and fragmentation, it is a very dynamic market that was limited by several barriers in the past. The installed capacity for BIPV has been predominantly driven by rooftop installations in residential, commercial, and industrial sectors, supported by national feed-in tariff schemes in countries like France, Italy, and Switzerland over the past decade. Recent advancements in technology and significant cost reductions both on product and process level using Building Information Model (BIM) have spurred the adoption of photovoltaic façades.

a. Today main markets.

As discussed in previous sections, the BIPV market is very diversified and difficult to monitor due to its complexity and fragmentation. However recent studies shows that the market is still in its initiation phase and if compared with the market of conventional photovoltaic systems (ground mounted or roof added systems) the current volume of BIPV can be estimated around 1 or 2% of the global photovoltaic market, with an estimated capacity of about 2.3 GW representing about 28 Billion US dollars in 2024. Despite being a niche market, the prospects are promising⁸⁴.

However, with sharp declines in solar costs, increased panel efficiency and new business models, BIPV could become the most popular residential solar option.

As reported by Solar Power Europe in 2022 the photovoltaic roof-top market represented about 60% of the total market in Europe and in 2023 they calculated to reach 66% of the market⁸⁵. Available solutions in this segment showcase a great variety of technical, economical and visual characteristics from in-roof mounting PV systems relying on semi-standard PV modules through the use of specific

mounting structures through building accessories integrated PV to patterned, coloured and semi-transparent BIPV façades as presented in previous sections.

In recent years, however, thanks to the sharp reduction in the cost of the technology, but especially thanks to the introduction of new technical solutions on the market that make BIPV systems similar to traditional building product has led to the spread of photovoltaic solar façades in some markets. Thanks to the implementation of photovoltaics in façades, it is possible to increase photovoltaic production during the early and late hours of the day and during wintertime (see Fig. 7a), as the sun is lower in the sky is favorable as the need of electricity is higher in winter in cold countries. Another great opportunity offered by façade-integrated solutions is the large surface area available in tall buildings, in particular BIPV façade are needed for Net-Zero Energy Buildings (NZEB) with a height of more than four floors, where the roof area is too small to power the house and often already dedicated to the implementation of ventilation and heating systems and above 10 floors, the construction will not reach anymore the NZEB^{86,87}.

For what concerns the diffusion of the market on a regional level, although we do not have objective data available, thanks to what we can gather from the main platforms on solar and BIPV architecture (such as solarchitecture.ch, Eurac platform, BIPV Netherlands platform, IEA PVPS and SHC platform and others), the countries where the BIPV market is more mature and consistent are Switzerland and the Netherlands, followed by China. China is promoting new solar buildings archetypes, innovations and large-scale projects that are driving the market, making Asia pacific a highly lucrative region for BIPV investments. Other European countries such as Italy, Germany and France also seem to be interested in developing the BIPV sector, but regulatory or economic barriers tend to hinder its development.

Figure 7. BIPV performance & market and Building Information Model (BIM). **a** | Photovoltaic electricity production on a sunny summer day in Germany with 20° inclined south (i-S) and vertical east-west (v-EW)⁸⁸. **b** | Performance of a façade mounted PV system⁸⁹. **c** | BIPV power and value market in Europe (covering EU-27 + UK + CH + NO). **d** | BIM has several advantages for the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) sector, the different stakeholder can use Common Data Environment (CDE) and single source to share data, while providing the right information during

the whole process. [BIPV market is exponentially growing and Building Information Model is a compulsory path for BIPV to be fully integrated in construction sector]. [Figure adapted from](#) ^{90,91}.

b. Potential market & Growth prospect

New multifunctional applications, integration methods and technological advancement, i.e. the use of new materials to improve module systems such as perovskite solar cells will make BIPV more appealing for architects, planners and building owners. New solution such as multifunctional building elements, solar controlled shading elements⁹ or lightweight solutions will certainly lead to further market growth with an estimated turnover of approximately 88 Billions dollars by 2030⁹² (Source Building-integrated Photovoltaics Market Size, Trends, Share, Growth | Report 2022-2030), and 130 to 143 billion US \$ by 2032^{93,94}.

Together with technology, digitalization is reshaping the construction sector, offering benefits such as reduced delays, cost control, and enhanced collaboration. Building Information modelling (BIM) stands as the cornerstone of this transformation, ensuring coherence in building realization, including the integration of BIPV in architects design since the early stage of the project.

BIM is used in the BIPV process. As indicated by the IEA PVPS Task 15 research⁹¹ the ideal BIPV process stage starts with the strategic planning of the building, where the client sets building objectives, including a budget, sustainability targets, energy accreditations and incentives. Iterative conceptual design follows, and the client, architect, BIPV / ESD consultant investigate the feasibility of different BIPV solutions through conceptual drawings, preliminary data, and simulations. This iteration continues in the developed design stage where the BIPV / ESD consultant, architect and the client investigate BIPV design scenarios and BIPV product solutions in more detail to obtain a preliminary/schematic project. Once a BIPV solution has been agreed, all involved BIPV stakeholders prepare detailed technical drawings, schedules, and specifications to enable the construction of the selected BIPV design. After the manufacturing stage is completed, based on the technical drawings the materials needed for the BIPV realization are shipped to the project site. The BIPV envelope is then built based on the technical drawings, specifications and instructions for installation, while the monitoring and controlling of the BIPV project installation process is carried out during the construction phase. Hence, testing and commissioning of the BIPV system is done and the building with BIPV project information is handed over to the building operators. The latest phase before the end of life is represented by the O&M where monitoring should be conducted in order to quantify BIPV energy performances.

Based on the BIPV process stages described and the recognized advantages of BIM for the AEC sector, the possible applications of BIM for BIPV and related benefits are described and summarized in the following diagram.

c. Patent & Innovation

The BIPV patent applications and grants during the last decades have depended on the national regulations and local market evolution. A recent report from the IEA-PVPS Task 15 compares the BIPV patents applied (and granted) in seven countries⁹⁵. An outstanding example is Italy, with many applied patents, most of them for mounting systems for roofs, which needed “innovative features” to justify access to higher tariffs. The BIPV roof products market was also predominant in other countries, such as the Netherlands, having a significant number of patents applied and granted.

6. Summary and future perspectives

As a summary, building integrated photovoltaic (BIPV) transforms the simple buildings' surface into a silent, still, clean, local, and potentially invisible energy production. Being part of building and PV environment, the BIPV module has to fulfil both construction and as a photovoltaic standard and regulations. Over the last decade, the cost of standard PV modules was reduced by 90% and its efficiency increased by more than 25%, transforming the solar energy from an expensive ecological source to a low-cost energy, competing with fossil fuel prices. At the same time, the PV technology

become nearly invisible with fine or hidden connectors and reliable coloring techniques. Thereby, different products and companies are present on the market enlarging the possibilities for architects and general buildings contractors to implement BIPV. Two extreme cases of BIPV projects exist with at first iconic buildings with unique BIPV element and secondly standardized BIPV element that can adapt easily on roof or façades for easier project replication. The carbon impact (CI) is 10 times smaller for south facing roof compared to EU27 energy mix and the net present value (NPV) is always positive apart for north-facing façade and ranged from 200 to 1800 €/m² for roof installation in Europe with top scorer countries being logically in the south. BIPV is very interesting and needs agility and flexibility as it takes place at the border of the objective PV system productivity and the subjective architect emotional rendering.

a. Potential of BIPV.

With climate change, high pressure is placed on the limitation of greenhouse gas (GHG) emission, but nowadays economic growth and GHG emission are directly interlinked^{96,97}. With the massive change toward renewable photovoltaic energy production this correlation should be removed⁹⁸. Solar energy has an exponential growth and represents today about 20% of the total renewable energy production (including hydro-power, without hydro it is about 40% of the renewable energy production)⁹⁹. The proportion of PV energy production is expected to increase as the total annual shipment represents today about 500 GW and should reach 1.5 TW in 10 years²⁵. As PV is an extensive energy production, it takes some surface: 500 GW represents 2'500 km², approximatively the surface of Tokyo. If PV starts to be in competition with existing usage of the land surface like agriculture, forest, recreative areas, industrial or residential surfaces quick tension and issue will rise. This is the reason why some synergies need to be found for example PV can cover and provide energy as the same time. In parallel, if one looks at the global energy consumption (GEC), the residential sector is today already representing more than 30% of the GEC, if we add the industrial sector we reach over 65% of GEC^{100,101}. By producing the energy locally the losses are reduced in the electricity grid¹⁰². Following this logic, roof-top apposed installation stand for 30% of the total application of PV where building integrated PV is today only 1%²⁵. In 10 years, BIPV market should be multiplied by 15 and represent 5% (with 75 GW) of the global PV market in surface (which means a proportion multiplied by 4 or 5 in value compared to mainstream PV) and roof-top apposed installation 25% (with 375 GW), so we can expect a large increase in BIPV market in the coming years²⁵. At a larger view, one can calculate the maximal limit of annual energy production from the building's environment. In Switzerland, it is expected that the economically exploitable BIPV potential is 67 TWh/y including 50 TWh/y from roof and 17 TWh/y from façades, which is in good correlation to the electricity annual need from Switzerland with 50 TWh/y¹⁰³. The consumption and production will not be aligned but can be stabilized with hydropower production in winter and peak-shaving in summer, this strategy could reduce by 85% de energy carbon intensity¹⁰³. At Europe level, modelling results indicate that the current rooftop PV technical potential could be about 2.7 PWh¹⁰⁴. Globally, to our knowledge there is no publication on the topic, but if we take the total surface of residential buildings of 260 billions m² and commercial buildings of 43.2 billion m²¹⁰⁵ equipped with 200 W/m² PV modules (20% module efficiency) of and a global average PV energy yield of 1370 kWh/kWp¹⁰⁶ this represents more than 3 times the global annual electricity demand of 27'700 TWh¹⁰⁷. By covering a third of the buildings surface with BIPV, the global annual electricity demands can be produced.

d. Next generation of PV cells

As the trend is toward high efficiency, the next generation of PV cells will be based on multi-junctions solar cells to capture with better efficiency the solar spectrum, like for example the promising tandem perovskite-silicon PV cells^{108,109}. This technology has the advantage to be based on the standard silicon cell with a relative low price top cell, but today the long term reliability is the biggest challenge¹¹⁰. An important surface of the skyscraper buildings is the windows; alternative PV technologies, like organic photovoltaics (OPV)¹¹¹⁻¹¹³ or luminescent solar concentration (LSC)^{114,115}

have the advantage of being semi-transparent possibly with colouring effects. For OPV recent publication show about 2.3% conversion efficiency for a 10 cm² semi-transparent mini-module with 70% total transparency¹¹⁶. Stability of OPV under direct sunlight and harsh outdoor environment is still a concern^{117,118} an alternative usage of OPV in buildings would be for indoor applications¹¹⁹. The LSC is based on a semi-transparent plate containing fluorescent materials with PV cells on the edges, it is perfectly suited as active windows and can show interesting performance up to 6.8% conversion efficiency on 30x30 cm²¹²⁰ and lower efficiency of 1.3% for larger windows of 150 x 100 cm²¹²¹, this show a some potential of LSC for transparent BIPV element¹²².

d. Ubiquitous PV

This overview demonstrated the large variety of active photovoltaics elements for buildings application like standard full-black PV module apposed on roofs representing the major part of PV for buildings, then perfectly designed solar-tiles invisible from the ground, colored double-glass BIPV element for façade application, or balconies based on bifacial PV module and finally semi-transparent canopy based of spaced crystalline solar cells. But much more is needed to slow down the climate change and the integration of PV should be ubiquitous starting with the sector with the largest surface under the sun, like residential and commercial buildings, large infrastructure as parking, roads, rails, noise barrier and dam. Agriculture has a huge potential with an initial PV integration on the greenhouse and on sensitive culture like fruit trees and berries. Agri-voltaism has advantages like reducing the watering thanks to limited evaporation, protecting the culture against hail and heat waves for examples^{123,124}. Another interesting sector for PV integration is the mobility with the change toward electric fuel. The integration can be on the car or truck surface^{125,126} or directly on charging station or on the garage's roof¹²⁷. With the internet of things (IoT) and autonomous systems, decentralized charging system is required and PV is a simple source of independent electricity production also for indoor applications¹²⁸.

Glossary

Building Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV)
Internet of things (IoT)
Organic photovoltaics (OPV)
Luminescent solar concentration (LSC)
Greenhouse gas (GHG)
Global energy consumption (GEC)
Net present value (NPV)
Carbon impact (CI)
Building Information modelling (BIM)
Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC)
Common Data Environment (CDE)
Net-Zero Energy Buildings (NZEB)
Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)
Balance of System (BOS)
End of Life (EOL)
Digital ceramic printing (DCP)
Perovskite Solar Cells (PSC)
Amorphous Silicon (a-Si)
Crystalline Silicon (c-Si)
Monocrystalline silicon (m-Si)
Multi-crystalline silicon (mc-Si)
Hydrogenated amorphous silicon (H:a-Si)
Silicon Heterojunction (SHJ)
Passivated Rear and Emitter Contact (PERC)
Tunnel Oxide Passivated Contact (TOPCon)

Cadmium telluride (CdTe)
Indium-gallium-copper selenide (CIGS)

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Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Author contributions

C.B. got the invitation and wrote the abstract. A.R. led the writing of the introduction. N.M.C. led the writing of the section 2. A.Sco. led the writing of the section 3. A.V, A.Sch. and L.M. led the writing of the section 4. F.F. led the writing of section 5. A.F. led the writing of section 6, organized the preparation of the meetings and coordinated the writing. All authors reviewed and edited the manuscript.